

SPONTANEOUS PERIRENAL HEMORRHAGE IN A PATIENT ON AN ANTICOAGULANT FOR STROKE WITH SEVERE AORTIC VALVE STENOSIS: IS CONCERN FOR RENAL MALIGNANCY

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ABSTRACT Spontaneous perirenal hemorrhage is mainly due to renal malignancy. But its presence in a patient who are on anticoagulant make it challenging for the diagnosis. We report a case of 50-year-old man who presented with brain stroke and started on an anticoagulant. Post anticoagulant treatment he presented with flank fullness. On evaluation, he found to have right perirenal hematoma suspicious of renal malignancy and severely stenosed aortic valve. We did right nephrectomy and aortic valve replacement simultaneous and on histopathologically found to have papillary renal cell carcinoma.

KEYWORDS Renal cell carcinoma, Perirenal hematoma, Aortic valve stenosis, Nephrectomy, Aortic valve replacement

Introduction

Spontaneous perirenal haemorrhage is rare presentations of renal tumours.¹ Its presence in patients who are on anticoagulants makes it challenging to diagnose. We report a case of papillary renal cell carcinoma (RCC) patient who presented with a spontaneous perirenal haemorrhage and was on oral an anticoagulants for treatment of embolic stroke due to atrial fibrillation associated with severe aortic stenosis. The patient was planned for simultaneous right radical nephrectomy and aortic valve replacement (AVR), and both are done in a single sitting.

Case report

A 57-year-old man was referred to us because of fullness in right flank who was under treatment on oral an anticoagulant for stroke caused by atrial fibrillation due to severe aortic stenosis. On evaluation, he was found to have 19x16x18 cm right perirenal hematoma on ultrasonography, which was confirmed on contrast-enhanced computed tomography of abdomen and pelvis (CECT). On CECT there was an enhancement of contrast in the wall and septa of the renal hematoma with compression of the ipsilateral kidney. Subsequent diethylenetriamine pentaacetic acid (DTPA) scan showed a non-functioning right kidney and a normal left kidney. Computer tomography of thorax and echocardiography showed calcified aortic valve with severe aortic stenosis, concentric left ventricular hypertrophy.

In our patient, there was a dilemma whether this perirenal hemorrhage was solely a result of anticoagulant therapy or some malignancy was contributing to it. There was no visible tumour on imaging as kidney was seen separate from perirenal haemorrhage. Establishing the diagnosis of malignancy in the presence of such perirenal haemorrhage may be clinically challenging. However, as the hematoma did not resolve rapidly, a high possibility of a renal tumour was entertained. Hence a decision to perform right radical nephrectomy was made. Although optimal management of an acute case of perirenal haemorrhage

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Fig.1. Contrast- enhanced computer tomography of the abdomen shows large perirenal hematoma with enhancing wall(Horizontal arrow showing hematoma and a vertical arrow showing right kidney)

Fig.2. Computer tomography thorax shows calcified aortic valve (vertical arrow)

Fig.3.A. Gross specimen of nephrectomy showing a round shaped organized hematoma

Fig.3.B. Histopathological specimen showing papillary renal cell carcinoma showing papillae with stromal cores (horizontal arrow) containing macrophages (H&E, 10X)

causing hemodynamic compromise is angioembolization, an organized hematoma should be formally managed with partial or radical nephrectomy if symptomatic, arising in the setting of malignancy or having a risk of rebleeding in non-malignant cases.

A multidisciplinary decision was taken to perform simultaneous right nephrectomy and aortic valve replacement. An oral anticoagulant was stopped five days before the surgery and anticoagulation for that period was bridged with intravenous unfractionated heparin. The surgery was performed through a midline sternotomy and laparotomy. The aortic valve was replaced first after establishing cardiopulmonary bypass(CPB). The biocompatible prosthetic aortic valve was used. It was followed by right radical nephrectomy. Post-operative period was uneventful. Histopathological examination of the right nephrectomy specimen was of papillary renal cell carcinoma. The patient is on regular follow up and doing well.

Discussion

Papillary RCC constitutes 10% to 15% of all RCCs.[1] Spontaneous perirenal haemorrhage is rare presentations of a renal tumour. The incidence of perirenal haemorrhage in RCC is unknown. The common causes of spontaneous perirenal haemorrhage are a malignancy of the kidney such as angiomyolipoma and RCC. The probability of occurrence of perirenal hematoma is increased in patients of RCC who are on concomitant anticoagulant therapy.[2]

Previously patients who have diagnosed with malignancy and cardiac disease were managed in a staged manner. However recently there is a change in the management of these cases.[1] Usually there is increased operative risk for the non-cardiac procedure performed in patients who are having cardiac prob-

lems.[3] It has been shown in past that by delaying the malignant lesion resection may lead to increases in the tumour growth due to the immunosuppressive effect of CPB which is mostly performed during cardiac surgery.[4]

Additionally when the dual procedure is done in a single setting overall cost will decrease. Recently abundant literature has come up with the results of simultaneous operations involving cardiac lesions and cancers.[4],[5] The overall outcomes of combined procedures have demonstrated that it's both feasible and safe in carefully selected patients.[6]

According to American Society of Anesthesiology (ASA) grading our patient comes in class III risk category for anaesthesia.[7] Surgery like nephrectomy is an independent predictor with a moderate risk of in-hospital death .[8] While performing a noncardiac surgery like nephrectomy, valvular heart disease is a risk factor for increased perioperative fatal and nonfatal cardiac complications. Proceeding with noncardiac surgery in patients with uncorrected severe AS can have a mortality rate of 10%.[8]

With the knowledge that simultaneous heart surgery like coronary artery bypass surgery (CABG) or AVR and surgery of other organs like a malignant disease of stomach, and lung have been described, albeit sparsely in literature, simultaneous AVR and right radical nephrectomy was also performed.[3],[4],[5],[6]. This is the rare case report of performing nephrectomy for spontaneous perirenal hematoma suspected due to malignancy and AVR in a single setting. This case report implies that whenever a patient present with perirenal hematoma which is on an oral anticoagulant, renal malignancy is of highest probability and should be managed proactively. Our case also indicates that at times when a patient needs a renal surgery and has a surgically correctable cardiac lesion which requires post-surgery anticoagulation, simultaneous renal and cardiac surgery may be the safest option.

References

1. Albi G, del Campo L, Tagarro D. Wunderlich's syndrome: causes, diagnosis and radiological management. *Clin Radiol*. 2002 Sep;57(9):840-5.
2. Parameswaran B, Khalid M, Malik N. Wunderlich syndrome following rupture of a renal angiomyolipoma. *Ann Saudi Med* 2006;26:310-12.
3. Foster ED, Davis KB, Carpentier JA, Abele S, Fray D. Risk of noncardiac operation in patients with defined coronary disease: The Coronary Artery Surgery Study (CASS) registry experience. *Ann Thorac Surg*. 1986;41:42-50.
4. Takahashi T, Nakano S, Shimazaki Y, Kaneko M, Nakahara K, Miyata M, et al. Concomitant Coronary Bypass Grafting and Curative Surgery for Cancer. *Surg Today*. 1995;25:131-135.
5. Litmathe J, Atmaca N, Menghesha D, Krian A. Combined procedures using the extracorporeal circulation and urologic tumor operation – experiences in six cases. *Interact Cardiovasc Thorac Surg*. 2004;3:132-135.
6. Fu Q, Li QZ, Liang DG, Ruan XH, Wang ZX, Wei MX. Early and long-term results of combined cardiac surgery and neoplastic resection in patients with concomitant severe heart disease and neoplasms. *Chin Med J (Eng)* 2011;124:1939-1942.

7. Budrikis A, Jievaltas M, Al Assaad S, Kinduris S. Simultaneous nephrectomy and coronary artery bypass grafting through extended sternotomy. *J Cardiothorac Surg*. 2012; 7: 79.

8. Dripps RD, Lamont A, Eckenhoff JE. The role of anesthesia in surgical mortality. *JAMA* 1961, 178:261-266. (ASA classification)